

INTEGRATIVE TEACHING METHODOLOGY OF BIOPHYSICS IN MEDICAL FIELDS

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Abstract. This article examines the scientific and physical methodology of applying biophysics to medicine in higher medical education institutions. This methodology is used to substantiate the relevance of this field for future medical professionals.

Keywords: medicine, physics, integration, practice, deformation.

Introduction: The social mandate for higher medical education institutions undoubtedly requires students to develop a deep and solid knowledge of physics, the ability to independently supplement this knowledge, and creatively apply it in medical practice. During deformation, the particles of a body move relative to one another. The force that changes the shape or size of a body is called the deformation force. According to Newton's Third Law, a force equal in magnitude to this force and opposite in direction arises in the body; this force is called the elastic force.

Figure 1. Types of Body Deformations

It is important to note that modern general practitioner must possess a broad fundamental training, including skills and abilities in the diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of specialized and related diseases, self-education and continuous self-education, developed clinical thinking and a communist worldview, as well as the knowledge necessary for medical practice. General theoretical training plays an important role in this area, including the teaching of physics and the development of the physician's value orientations and motivation. Biomechanics is a branch of biophysics that studies the mechanical properties of living tissues and organs.

It is widely accepted that human tissues possess certain mechanical properties: strength, elasticity, fragility, etc. The mechanical properties of tissues depend on their composition and structure. During physiological activity, organs and their individual parts bear a certain mechanical load. Under the influence of these loads, tissues are deformed.

It is important to teach this topic to medical students in an integrated manner using the following topics (Figure 1).

Figure 2. Topics for studying the mechanical properties of living tissues and organs

One of the important mechanical properties of living tissues is strength. Strength is the property of resistance to damage. It is inversely proportional to the minimum breaking stress, which is a quantity.

Bone tissue has the greatest strength. $\delta_{\text{bone}} = 109 \text{ N/m}^2$

The strength of human bone is higher than that of Cu and Al, but lower than that of steel. In traumatology and orthopedics, it should be taken into account that the compressive strength of bone is 1.8 times greater than its tensile strength.

The methodology for preparing medical students to solve professional problems when teaching physics at a medical university is based on identifying and implementing the integrative links between physics and a number of medical and biological sciences, the principles of systemic professional development and integration, and the unity of the fundamental and professionally oriented components of the physics course.

In the process of teaching physics at a medical university, professionally oriented physics problems are used as a special tool for developing the ability of future doctors to solve professional problems.

It is based on the need and opportunity to prepare medical students to solve professional problems in the context of integrating physics with medical and biological sciences by developing professional integrative skills and abilities in future doctors to solve professional problems based on physical knowledge and skills, as well as mastering the fundamentals of physics.

Figure 3. Tissues and organs in the human body

Muscle strength depends on the number of fibers in it. This is measured using the physiological, rather than geometric, cross-sectional area of the muscle. The physiological cross-sectional area is equal to the sum of all the fibers that make up the muscle.

The human musculoskeletal system consists of interconnected skeletal bones, to which muscles are attached at specific points.

The skeletal bones act like levers. They have fulcrums at the joints and are moved by the force of gravity exerted by the muscles, which in turn is generated by their contraction.

Figure 4. Basic musculoskeletal system.

It follows from the above,:

1) education should be structured as a unified, integrated process aimed at consistently connecting general and specialized disciplines;

2) issues of the personal value aspect of education and an individual's attitude toward their education, its level, and quality are fundamental and important;

3) the use of innovative technologies, including didactic teaching aids aimed at realizing the value-semantic aspects of the educational material being studied (module, problem-based module, integrative module, modular learning type, personnel-based, etc.), is of great importance in the university educational process.

In connection with the modernization of the entire education system, the influence of value-semantic attitudes on improving the quality of students' knowledge requires additional research. Ensuring high-quality student training in medical and biological physics, a general subject for medical universities, is challenging due to persistent discrepancies between: modern requirements for the higher education system, the individual focus of its content, the implementation of value-semantic preferences at different stages of education, and the inadequacy of practical methods and means for their implementation; the urgent need to acquire solid, effective, and promising knowledge formed as a result of students' value-semantic orientation toward specialized disciplines, and the insufficient development of the theoretical conditions for their implementation in the educational process; the need to use new teaching methods and pedagogical technologies aimed at realizing students' value-semantic attitudes in interaction with each other, and the insufficient development of the methods and means for their implementation.

In conclusion: It is generally assumed that the levels, criteria, and indicators of the development of the ability to solve professional problems based on physical knowledge and skills are determined. The structure and content of the ability to solve professional problems based on physical knowledge and skills as a professional integrative skill are revealed. The skill structure

includes a content component (physical knowledge necessary for solving professional problems) and a process component (physical skills necessary for solving professional problems). The skill includes three personal skills: the ability to solve preventive, diagnostic, and therapeutic problems based on physical knowledge and skills.

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